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Proof-of-concept of a Realistic Solar Sail Propelled CubeSat Class Spacecraft Digital Twin Targeting Orbits around Mars and its Moons

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List of Symbols

- .stl** A file format commonly used for 3D printing and computer-aided design (CAD). 55
- ADCS** Abbreviation of “Attitude Determination and Control Software”. 10, 11
- apoapsis** A planet, asteroid, or comet’s closest point in its orbit to the Sun. 56
- area of influence** Space of the planets that are influenced by their mass. 17
- Argument of periapsis** The ellipse’s orientation in the orbital plane is defined by the argument of periapsis, which is an angle measured from the ascending node to the periapsis. 22
- Attitude Control** Control of the rotational motion of the spacecraft. 17
- Attitude Dynamics** Rotational motion of the spacecraft. 8
- Bezier Circle** A type of continuous or polynomial curve that is widely used in computer graphics, animation, and design. 56
- Blender** An animation and visualization software. 8, 51
- CPU** A complex set of electronic circuitry that runs the machine’s operating system and apps. 59
- Digital Twin** A dynamic virtual simulation. 8
- Eccentricity** Numerical description of the shape of the ellipse, describing how much it is elongated compared to a circle. 22
- Elgiloy** A non-magnetic non-corrosive super alloy. 20
- FOSS** Abbreviation of “Free Open Source Software”. 8
- gyroscope** Devices that are used for orientation and angular momentum by spinning. 21

LEO Abbreviation of “Low Earth Orbit”. Orbits which have an altitude less than 2000 km are called LEO. 17

Lightsail 2 It is a project that uses a CubeSat to demonstrate controlled solar travel in Low Earth Orbit. 10, 38

luminosity Measurement of the light per unit time. 28

momentum wheel Devices that generate torque for rotational motion. 21

Mylar A polyester film made from stretched polyethylene terephthalate (PET). 20

Orbital Dynamics Translational motion of the spacecraft. 8

payload Mass of the spacecraft beside the mass of the sail, the ribs and the deployment mechanism. 20

PD Proportional-Derivative controller. 41

periapsis An orbiting body’s closest point in its route to the body it orbits. 56

PID Proportional-Integral-Derivative controller. 47

Scilab A free open source software for mathematical modelling. 8

Sinclair Interplanetary A brand under Rocketlab that produces star trackers and reaction wheels. 38

SMA Semimajor axis; half the distance between periapsis and apoapsis. 22

solar radiation power Power that is generated by the solar radiation acting on sail. 17

transfer function Ratio of the Laplace transformation of the response function to the Laplace transformation of the driving function. 40

versor A versor is a vector (or quaternion) with unit length. 36

Wolfram Free Engine (WFE) A free computation tool. 8

Xcos A program for modeling dynamic systems and solving numerical equations based on blocks. 8

Abstract

In order to prove the concept of a realistic solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting orbits around Mars and its moons, a digital twin is built. Digital twins are new technological improvements that reduce project expenses and bring the unexpected outcomes of real applications into the digital universe. In this project, the digital twin is developed based on three subjects, orbital dynamics, attitude dynamics, and visualization. Orbital dynamics and attitude dynamics are simulated via Xcos. The visualization process is accomplished via Blender. Orbital dynamics include the orbit around the Sun and Mars. Meanwhile, attitude dynamics cover the rotation of the sail to control the thrust by solar radiation pressure. By considering the random and bias effects, the realistic attitude control is simulated. The mission, the design, and the actuator are also explained. With Blender, scenes are processed frame by frame to get realistic animations.

1 Introduction

Mars missions have been one of the main subjects of the space race since the 20th century [15]. To reach Mars, different studies have been done throughout the years including this [16] [17]. Also, several examples of solar sail applications are attached in the references [18] [19] [20] [21]. In this project, the concept of a realistic solar-sail propelled Cubesat class spacecraft targeting around Mars and its moons is proven by building a digital twin. The concept of the solar sail is a new approach to the space age that works without fuel, engine, or motor. Solar radiation pressure acting on a sail can generate a thrust for space travel. Although different works have been done in previous years for solar sailing, this project has a greater perspective in terms of the mission frame. In this project, a Digital Twin that is a dynamic virtual simulation is built for the purpose. While the simulations of the spacecraft dynamics and visualization of dynamics are subjects of this paper, navigation of the mission is studied by Kıymet Yıldır [22] and trajectory design is studied by Muratcan Yurttaş, Bora Atakan, Sila Simay Mumcuoğlu [23].

The digital twin is created based on mathematical modeling, simulations, and visualization by using only FOSS. For numerical calculations, Wolfram Free Engine (WFE), for modeling and simulations, Scilab/Xcos, and for visualization, Blender are used.

In spacecraft terminology, the translational motion of the spacecraft is called “Orbital Dynamics”, and the rotational motion is called “Attitude Dynamics”. Orbital dynamics and attitude dynamics are the two main subjects of spacecraft mechanics in this project. In orbital dynamics, orbital mechanics of the sail such as orbit evolution with solar radiation pressure around the Sun and Mars are explained and simulated. Another point that is discussed in orbital dynamics is Mars’s arrival and aerobraking. In attitude dynamics, the rotation of the sail to control the radiation pressure acting on the sail is modeled and simulated. Based on the outputs, the digital twin is visualized in Blender. To get the realistic animations Blender scenes are processed frame by frame.

The following sections include the literature reviews regarding solar sailing and digital twin issues, the mission process, designing, modeling, simulating, and visualization processes.

Before that, the term “Digital Twin” is explained below.

1.1 Digital Twin

A common definition of a digital twin is still lacking. A digital twin can be described in a variety of ways, depending on its intended use and extent. A digital twin is a system that combines a computational model with an actual system to optimize, control, and monitor its operation. A digital twin can acquire the ability to be independent and to absorb information from and make sense of its surroundings through data and feedback, both real and simulated. [24] The digital twin's added value increased dramatically from its beginnings as a strategy with strong commercial impact, and as a result, it attracted increasing attention and significance across numerous businesses and industries. [25]

2 Literature Review

2.1 D. A. Spencer et. al. “The LightSail 2 Solar Sailing Technology Demonstration” [1]

The LightSail project is a decade-long program sponsored by The Planetary Society. While LightSail 1 was a try for the on-orbit functionality of the solar sail, Lightsail 2 is a fully developed solar sail that orbits the Earth.

The LightSail 2 is designed as a 3U CubeSat and fabricated by Stellar Exploration, Incorporated. The solar sail has a 32 m² of sail area with a mass of 5kg. The sail is made of Mylar and is 4.6 μm thick. 4 meters of Triangular Retractable And Collapsible (TRAC) booms that are made of elgiloy are used for deployment of the sail. The LightSail 2 is made of 15 subsystems.

The solar arrays, batteries, power distribution, and fault protection circuits make up the electrical power subsystem. An average of 8.5 W is produced by a solar panel system and a 5.6 Ah battery pack. Solar power is fed by a set of 8 lithium-polymer batteries during the eclipse period. Attitude control by using the magnetic field of the Earth is done via three magnetotors, one in each body axis. Two Planetary Society Cameras (PSCAMs) are also placed at the tips of opposing solar panels.

Magnetometers are positioned close to the tips of each deployable solar panel, sun sensors are situated on the -Z panel and at the points of each deployable solar panel, and gyros that measure three-axis angular rates are housed in the avionics compartment.

C programming language is used to write the flight software and firmware of LightSail. Another important part of the LightSail 2 is ADCS “Attitude Determination and Control System”. The ADCS which is written in MATLAB/Simulink and autogenerated to C code is used to control the torque and momentum wheel. The attitude control mechanism also commands the Microchip Payload Interface Card (PIC) for sail deployment.

Another important content of this paper regarding the project is solar sailing performance. The LightSail 2 is oriented to its solar sails relative to the Sun. This orientation includes a cycle of “On-Off” that results in the spacecraft slewing in the Y axis.

The “On” position represents the attitude when the sails are facing the Sun, so the thrust is at maximum meanwhile in the “Off” position the thrust is minimum. Sail control is optimized based on the data that comes from magnetometer and sun sensor measurements. The command versus the flight data is the significant output of this paper.

According to the outputs of the plot, the LightSail 2 project is declared as a success. With the “On-Off” mechanism, apogee increases and perigee decreases.

In conclusion, the LightSail 2 has completed its goals for the program. With the control strategy, LightSail 2 made a great contribution to solar sailing technology. Further information and figures can be found in Reference [1].

2.2 J. R. Mansell et. al. “LightSail 2 Solar Sail Control and Orbit Evolution” [2]

All of the solar sail missions are provided by the orientation to control the solar radiation pressure on the sail. So, the attitude control of the solar sail is one of the most important points of the technology readiness level (TRL) of the project.

The formation of the CubeSat can cause benefits and disadvantages when it comes to simulate the attitude determination and control system (ADCS) to control the sail. The paper aims to explain the developments and assess the ADCS of the LightSail 2 mission.

The hardware of the ADCS of the LightSail 2 includes two magnetometers, one of the two sets of gyros processed by an extended Kalman filter that provides the attitude information, and five sun sensors.

On the +X and +Y solar panels, the magnetometers were placed. Also, on the end of each deployable panel, there was one sun sensor placed such that their 75° (half-cone) fields of view overlapped about the -Z axis. The last sun sensor was put on the -Z face of the spacecraft body on a solar panel. Between the sun sensors, there was a decision-making collaboration not to measure that were beyond the 3σ noise characteristic of the sensors. This was a crucial point since the intensity of the source that was measured was not red because of the configuration of the sensors. That is why when at least one sensor does not see the Sun, ingestion by the attitude filter does not happen by the sensors.

At the beginning, the solar sails were stowed against the spacecraft but deployed at 155 degrees to have the configuration. A difference was the +Y panel. Beginning in 2020, images showed that the +Y panel had deployed only partially.

A rotation of 92° was needed to reduce the average angular discrepancy between the measurements of the +X and +Y magnetometer in the spacecraft body frame. Sun sensor and rotation matrices of the sensor-to-body frame for the +Y magnetometer were subsequently incorporated into this correction.

Table 1: LightSail 2 ADCS components

Component	Manufacturer	Metric	Value
Magnetometers	Honeywell	1σ noise	$0.2\mu\text{T}$
Sun sensors	Elmos	Resolution	2.7 deg
Primary gyros	Analog Devices	1σ noise	0.27 deg/s
Momentum wheel	Sinclair Interplanetary	Max RPM	5920
		Max Torque	5×10^{-3} Nm
Torque rods	Stras Space	Max Dipole	1 Am ²
		Duty Cycle	700 ms/s

Table 2: LightSail 2 spacecraft characteristics

Mass	Value
Mass	4.93 kg
Sail area	32 m ² (square)
Sail Loading	154 g m ⁻²
Volume of bus	3U (10 × 10 × 30 cm)
Moments of inertia	$I_x=3.79$ kg m ² , $I_y=3.79$ kg m ² , $I_z =7.33$ kg m ²
Products of inertia	$I_{xy}=-1.90 \times 10^{-4}$ kg m ² , $I_{xz} = -8.18 \times 10^{-4}$ kg m ² $I_{yz}=1.47 \times 10^{-3}$ kg m ²

Either the mainboard gyros or a set of three primary (PIB) gyros measured the angular rates to support the sun sensors and magnetometers. The mainboard gyros were only used in spacecraft modes that did not require attitude knowledge since they were uncalibrated. The PIB gyros provided rates to an accuracy of $\sigma = 0.27$ deg/s even though they required higher power.

The attitude was controlled with a magnetic torque rod on every axis and a momentum wheel actuating about the +Y axis. The wheel prevents the turn about the Y axis from being conducted for a few minutes, while the torque rods balance the other axis and realize momentum management. Lastly, the sail was built of booms upon deployment, for a total area of 32m². The Mylar was covered with aluminum on the -Z side of the sail.

The tables above show the main ADCS components and characteristics of the spacecraft. The ADCS control loop operated at 1 Hz. In every 5 min, the telemetry was logged but could be collected up to 0.2 Hz upon command.

The ADCS software had 6 operational modes. Every mode used an extended Kalman filter to determine the attitude. Either the mainboard or PIB

gyros were processed by the filter with the magnetometers and sun sensors according to the mode. Whenever the TLE data shows the LightSail 2 is in eclipse, the filter was commanded not to take into consideration the sun sensors. Mode detumble (mode 0) used a B-dot algorithm to authorize the torque rods to oppose the spacecraft orientation, caught by differencing successive magnetometer measurements in the spacecraft body frame. The mode also can work with not sufficient attitude knowledge from the Kalman filter. Actively controlled modes were modes 2,4 and 5. Based on the spacecraft velocity and inertial position of the Sun, modes made a command quaternion. Thus, it was essential to these modes an accurate quaternion estimate from the Kalman filter.

The most used mode was the solar sailing mode (mode 2). This mode operated the slew of LS2 between two attitudes. When getting far from the Sun, LS2 pointed the sail normal vector (+Z) anti-parallel to the Sun. “On” attitude is the result of this slew and provided the maximum solar radiation pressure on the sail and projects the thrust in a direction that boosted the energy of the orbit. On the other hand, “Off” attitude resulted with the least thrust on the other half of the orbit.

In no-torque mode (mode 3), the spacecraft batteries were able to recharge before re-engaging the momentum wheel.

After the long mission of the LightSail 2, in early 2022 it was deorbited due to the loose of the On-Off control.

Further information and figures regarding the article can be found in Reference [2].

2.3 A. J. Tang, X. Wu “An Interplanetary Mission Design of a Solar Sailing CubeSat to Mars” [3]

A thorough examination of the viability of an interplanetary mission to Mars employing solar sailing technology can be found in the 2020 Journal of Physics: Conference Series paper “An Interplanetary Mission Design of a Solar Sailing CubeSat to Mars”. With a focus on the potential of solar sails as the main propulsion system for interplanetary missions, the study focuses on the numerical analysis of orbital transfers to Mars using solar sails and attitude control. To reduce the requirement for chemical propulsion for orbital insertion, the use of solar sails as drag sails for aerobraking capture is also covered in the paper.

An overview of solar sailing technology is given in the study, along with information on the evolution of solar sail missions and their history. Different

solar sail designs and technology demonstrators are also examined. In addition, it provides orbital capture and trajectory analysis for the interplanetary coast at the intended destination, emphasizing how solar sails can transform interplanetary travel by cutting down on transfer times and offering a substitute for conventional propulsion systems.

The study's findings suggest that solar sail designs of the present and the future can transit to and be captured within a Martian orbit by using aerobraking and solar radiation pressure; potential transfer times could be shorter than those of traditional Hohmann and one tangent burn transfers trajectories that are achievable with current chemical propulsion. The study also highlights how solar sails could lessen the need for conventional chemical propulsion systems, providing an economical and effective way to travel to places like Mars.

The study concludes by arguing that solar sailing technology offers a low-cost and environmentally friendly way to explore space and may end up serving as interplanetary missions' main propulsion system. The study also emphasizes the necessity of additional investigation and advancement to verify the suggested models and polish the technology in preparation for real-world application.

The paper highlights the efficiency of aerobraking capture techniques for solar sailing spacecraft, offering a feasible substitute for chemical propulsion for orbital insertion. It also explores the potential of solar sails to shorten transfer times and offer an alternative to conventional propulsion systems. According to the study, solar sailing technology has the potential to completely transform interplanetary travel by providing a practical and economical means of getting to places like Mars. A major development in space exploration is the potential for solar sails to shorten transfer times and offer an alternative to conventional propulsion systems. Overall, the paper offers a thorough analysis of solar sailing technology's potential for interplanetary missions, stressing its advantages and viability for upcoming space missions. It highlights how solar sails can lessen the need for conventional chemical propulsion systems, providing an economical and effective way to travel to places like Mars. To validate the suggested models and improve the technology for real-world use, more study is advised.

Further information and figures can be found at [3].

2.4 O. Mori, H. Sawada, R. Funase et. al. “First Solar Power Sail Demonstration by IKAROS” [4]

A major development in space exploration, particularly in the design of solar power sails for interplanetary missions, is represented by the paper “First Solar Power Sail Demonstration by IKAROS” by O. Mori et al. This innovative mission was started by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) to show that solar sails can be used to generate power and propel spacecraft.

The Interplanetary Kite-craft Accelerated by Radiation of the Sun, or IKAROS mission, set out to demonstrate how solar sails could be used to harness solar radiation pressure for propulsion. Since this technology doesn’t require onboard fuel, it presents a promising substitute for conventional rocket propulsion. Rather, photons from the Sun are captured and reflected by the sail, creating a constant thrust that allows the spacecraft to travel through space.

Using thin-film solar cells integrated into the sail membrane was one of the main innovations of the IKAROS mission. These amorphous silicon solar cells were intended to provide power for the spacecraft’s systems, such as its navigation and communication apparatus. This illustrated how solar sails can be used as both a propulsion and a power generation system.

Another crucial component of the mission was the IKAROS sail’s deployment mechanism. The sail membrane was intended to be stored in a rolled-up configuration, as the spacecraft was intended to be a spinner. Spin centrifugal force was used to deploy the sail once it reached space, which assisted in unfolding the membrane to its full diameter of 20 meters. This deployment technique was a fresh approach that worked well to keep the sail stable and in the proper shape throughout the mission.

Deploying the IKAROS sail was yet another crucial component of the mission. With the sail membrane stored in an averted position, the spacecraft was intended to be a spinner. The membrane unfolded to its full 20-meter diameter upon reaching space thanks to the spin centrifugal force that was used to deploy the sail. The sail’s stability and form were successfully maintained throughout the mission with the help of this innovative deployment technique.

In conclusion, the IKAROS mission marked a groundbreaking development in solar power sail technology. It provided evidence that solar sails could be used to generate power and propel spacecraft, creating new avenues for sustainable and affordable space travel. The IKAROS mission’s success opened the door for further developments in solar sail technology, which could be used in a variety of space missions. It is the first spacecraft to successfully demonstrate solar sail technology in interplanetary space.

Further information and figures can be found at [4].

3 Methodology

3.1 The Mission

The mission of this project is to go to Mars with using a solar-sail. One of the most important aims of the mission is to prove the concept of interplanetary solar sail missions. The mission can be separated into three parts, The Earth, the Sun, and Mars. The mission starts with a launch from the Earth. After the launch, the sail starts orbiting LEO. LEO or “low earth orbit” is an orbit with an altitude of less than 2000 km. Then the CubeSat leaves LEO and reaches the orbit of the Sun by interplanetary cruise under solar radiation power. It orbits the Sun to pump energy to the sails to generate thrust for arrival to Mars. This thrust generation needs to be controlled in order to end in the area of influence of Mars. Thrust generation is controlled via the orientation of the sail which is explained in the “Attitude Control” section. “On-Off” control commands provide the sail to maximize and minimize the thrust to increase the orbit in apoapsis to get closer to Mars and decrease the orbit in periapsis. In the last part of the mission, the spacecraft is in the area of influence of Mars. This time, the opposite approach of the orbital dynamics of the Sun happens. With the same On-Off control, periapsis increases and apoapsis decreases. These maneuvers end with the spacecraft landing on Mars via aerobraking.

Before going into the orbiting details, first, working principle and the history of the solar sailing must be explained.

3.1.1 Working Principle and History of Solar-Sail [5] [6]

History of Solar-sail

1600s–1800s: Light pressure propulsion in space was postulated by scientists including Johannes Kepler and James Clerk Maxwell.

1920s–1950s: In science fiction literature and theoretical works, Konstantin Tsiolkovsky and other visionaries expanded upon the idea of solar sails.

1970s–1980s: NASA and other space organizations started doing extensive studies on solar sails as a possible spaceship propulsion technology.

2000s–Present: A number of effective solar sail technology demonstrations have been carried out, including The Planetary Society’s LightSail programs and Japan’s IKAROS mission.

Through the integration of these mathematical formulas with the fundamental principles of solar sail physics, scientists and engineers can devise and

enhance solar sail spacecraft for diverse space exploration missions.

Working Principle of Solar Sail

Light is made up of photons. Although photons lack mass, they do have momentum as they travel through space. When light strikes a solar sail, which has a bright, mirror-like surface, the photons bounce off it (i.e. reflect off it, just like a mirror). As photons strike the sail, their momentum is transferred to it, providing it a slight push. As they bounce off the sail, the photons give it a slight push. Both pushes are relatively minor, but in the vacuum of space, where there is nothing to slow the sail, each push alters the sail's speed. When a solar sail confronts the Sun directly, photons propel the spaceship ahead, away from it. However, a solar sail can travel in different directions by tacking like a sailboat, which changes the angle of the sail relative to the Sun. It is even feasible to change the spacecraft's orbit around the Sun by angling the sail so that solar photons push against the direction of motion. Other methods for controlling the direction of solar sails include altering the centre of mass or utilising tip vanes.

The momentum of a photon given by;

$$p = \frac{E}{c}$$

E is the energy of a photon and c is the speed of light.

Photon pressure P is defined as the force exerted per unit area by the photons and is given by;

$$P = \frac{2E}{c}$$

The acceleration a experienced by a solar sail due to photon pressure can be calculated using Newton's second law $F = ma$;

$$F = PA$$

$ma = PA$ which gives us,

$$a = \frac{P}{m}$$

3.1.2 On-Off Control Strategy

The main control of the sail to cruise in space is the On-Off strategy which is also used in LightSail 2 for orbiting the Earth. On-Off commanding controls the orientation of the sail so, the radiation pressure acting on the sail can be

controlled. Assume the sail is in the perigee and it is parallel to the Sun. In this position, sunlight hits the sail with 90° which generates the maximum thrust. When the thrust needs to be minimized, On-Off control turns the sail 90 degrees which orients the sail perpendicular to the Sun. The new orientation is the “Off” position. In the apogee, an opposite orientation is needed. For that, -90 degrees of a turn is applied and the sail again becomes in the “On” position.

Attitude dynamics and the application of the control mechanism for the On-Off strategy are explained in Section 3.4.

3.1.3 Aerobraking [7]

Aerobraking is an astronomical technique to slow down the spacecraft due to atmospheric drag. Spacecraft employed the drag of the Martian atmosphere on its solar panels to slow down rather than employing thrusters, which need more fuel and hence add weight and cost. The duration of the aerobraking phase is proportional to how quickly Mars’ comparatively thin atmosphere reduces the spacecraft’s velocity. At the commencement of aerobraking, the solar panels were designed in a way that increased drag and slowed the spacecraft down. In addition, extra flaps at the end of the solar panel were unfurled to enhance drag. In this project, it is assumed that the aerobraking part is successfully done. After aerobraking, to approach to Mars Xcos diagram is explained in the Xcos Diagram of Approach to Mars Atmosphere section.

Figure 1: *Solar Sail Concept*

3.2 Design of the Satellite

The solar sail is designed to be launched from the Earth and to orbit Mars and its moons. It is designed based on mission requirements like navigation and purposes like solar sailing. The size of the solar sail is 900 m^2 with one edge being 30 m, a total mass of 40 kg, and the payload is 8 kg.

Figure 2: *A sketch of the Solar Sail*

The solar sail is designed based on four mass groups as explained in [26] [27]. The sail, four booms (or the ribs), deployment mechanism, and the payload. Spacecraft design characteristics such as mass, material, and volume are shown in the Table 3 below.

Table 3: Spacecraft characteristics

Part	Mass [kg]	Material	Volume [m^3] $\times 10^{-4}$
Sail	5.589	Mylar [28]	40.5
Ribs	22.638	Elgiloy [29]	21.3258
Deployment Mechanism	3.773	Aluminum alloy 6061 [30]	3.7609
Payload	8	Complex	68.1

The sail membrane is chosen as Mylar based on LightSail 2 [31]. In

LightSail 2, the membrane was $4.5 \mu\text{m}$ thick and it was orbiting LEO. In this project, the solar sail will reach to the Sun so the membrane thickness is designed as twice of LightSail 2, $9 \mu\text{m}$.

The payload includes solar panels, batteries, a gyroscope, and a momentum wheel which are the main parts of the attitude control and navigation. Solar panels are used to run the actuators while in the “On” position since they work with solar energy meanwhile, electrical energy is provided by the batteries in the off position. The momentum wheel is used as the actuator and it is run by the electrical energy provided by the solar panels and the batteries. Gyroscopes in the payload are used to determine the navigation. Another payload subsystem is sun sensors to determine the position with respect to the Sun. So that, the satellite can decide to start its attitude control.

3.2.1 Moment of Inertia Computation

In order to design a mechanism for attitude control, a moment of inertia is computed based on the mass and volume data given above.

Table 4: Parts and Moment of Inertia values

Part	Moment of Inertia
Sail	10060.2
Ribs	10620.3
Deployment Mechanism	0.00417268
Payload	0.0333333
Total	20680.5

The moment of inertia of each part and the total moment of inertia are shown in the Table 4 above.

3.3 Orbital Dynamics

3.3.1 Orbital Maneuvers [8]

Depending on the goals of the mission, a particular orbit or orbits are assigned for the satellite. Depending on the launch site and vehicle type, it can be possible to reach this orbit straight after launch or not. As a result, orbital maneuvers are frequently needed.

3.3.2 Coplanar Maneuvers

Assume for the moment that the starting and ending orbits are in the same plane. In this instance, altering the orbit's size, shape, and orientation inside the plane merely requires changing the orbital elements SMA, Eccentricity, Argument of periapsis. Modifications are limited to tangential velocity shifts, meaning that the amount of the velocity is the only one that needs to be altered and not its direction.

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{r} &= r\vec{x}_0. \\ \vec{v} &= \dot{r}\vec{x}_0 + r\dot{\theta}\vec{y}_0. \\ \dot{r} &= \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\alpha(1-e^2)}}e\sin\theta.\end{aligned}$$

This indicates that any change in tangential velocity at any point on a circular orbit causes that point to change to either apoapsis or periapsis in the new orbit. Any change in tangential velocity at periapsis causes a change in apoapsis height for an elliptical orbit, and any change in tangential velocity at apoapsis causes a change in periapsis height. Only during periapsis or apoapsis a tangential transfer to circularise an elliptical orbit is sought.

$$v = \sqrt{\mu\left(\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1}{a}\right)}.$$

3.3.3 Elliptical to Circular Transfer

Since the orbit around the Sun is elliptical and it is aimed at the orbit around Mars as circular, it is considered a transfer from an elliptical orbit (orbit 1) to a circular orbit (orbit 2). Either orbit 1's periapsis or apoapsis must serve as the transfer point. At the transfer point, the two orbits' orbital velocities are,

Figure 3: *Circular to Elliptical Transfer Adapted from de Ruiter's Spacecraft Dynamics and Control [8]*

$$v_1 = \sqrt{\mu \left(\frac{2}{r_2} - \frac{1}{a} \right)}.$$

$$v_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{r_2}}$$

If $a > r_2$ (transfer at orbital periapsis), $v_1 > v_2$, and the overall change in velocity equals

$$\Delta v = v_2 - v_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{r_2}} - \sqrt{\mu \left(\frac{2}{r_2} - \frac{1}{a} \right)}.$$

If $a < r_2$ (transfer at orbital apoapsis), $v_2 > v_1$, and the overall change in velocity equals

$$\Delta v = v_2 - v_1 = \sqrt{\mu \left(\frac{2}{r_2} - \frac{1}{a} \right)} - \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{r_2}}.$$

Figure 4: *Elliptical to Circular Transfer Adapted from de Ruiter's Spacecraft Dynamics and Control [8]*

3.3.4 Simulation of Solar-sail Orbiting the Sun [9]

Figure 5: *Xcos Diagram*

The motion of a spacecraft around a planet driven by solar sails can be replicated. The spacecraft will launch at a specific location and speed. One can calculate this elliptical movement by applying Newton's law of motion. Given these circumstances, the planet will have force on the spacecraft equal to the square of the distance divided by the product of the mass of the planet and the spacecraft. Xcos gives the orbit calculations from given circumstances, and the sail logic plot output from the simulation is taken.

Figure 6: *Sail Management Logic*

The yellow superblock is the product of velocity and distance, and this product helps understand the position of the solar sail in sail logic. If this product is equal to 0, it is understood that there are periapsis and apoapsis. In Figure 5 VMAG block sums the square of v_x and v_y values and gets the VMAG value. BEG and END step blocks control when the maneuver begins and ends.

Figure 7: *Sail-Logic Diagram*

This block diagram part is about sail-logic. This diagram decides when the solar-sail will be on and off position. When it is on position solar-sail faces to the Sun and collects the sunlight. When it is off position solar-sail turns back to the Sun and gets zero sunlight. When it is equal to zero, θ equals to 0 degrees, when it is equals to 1, θ equals to 90 degrees.

Figure 8: *Sail-Logic*

This plot shows when the solar-sail is on and off position. 0 = off, 1= on.

Figure 9: *K-Radiation Superblock*

This figure shows the blocks inside the k-rad superblock. From top to bottom, first block represents luminosity of the Sun, second block is the area of the solar-sail in this project real area of solar-sail is equals to $900m^2$, third block is spacecraft mass = 40 kg, and the other blocks are constant values pi, lightspeed, reflection coefficient.

Figure 10: *Orbit Around the Sun*

In this figure, it is shown that apoapsis is getting bigger and bigger in time and periapsis is getting smaller slowly, because of the sail-logic. This helps the solar-sail move away from the Sun.

Other blocks and superblocks are explained in detail in the Xcos Diagram of Approach to Mars Atmosphere section.

Maneuvers to approach the Martian atmosphere were created on this diagram. This Xcos diagram includes perturbed 2-body dynamics, radiation acceleration calculation, and sail-logic parts. All these parts of the diagram are explained below.

Figure 12: *Perturbed 2-Body Dynamics*

As shown in the Figure 11 , these blocks are calculating the 2-body dynamics. Position vector blocks are on the far right of the diagram ($x.y$). Velocity vector blocks are connected to these two blocks (v_x, v_y). These position and velocity block are taking the integral of the previous blocks to calculate acceleration and velocity.

$$x = 7098000m$$

$$y = 0m$$

$$v_x = 0m/s$$

$$v_y = 2700m/s$$

Figure 13: *K-Radiation Superblock*

This figure shows the blocks inside the k-rad superblock. From top to bottom, first block represents luminosity of the Sun, second block is the area of the solar-sail in this project real area of solar-sail is equals to $900m^2$ but to show the solar-sail orbit more clearly area multiplied by 100, third block is spacecraft mass = 40 kg, and the other blocks are constant values pi, lightspeed, reflection coefficient.

Figure 14: *Radiation Acceleration*

This block diagram gets values from the k-rad superblock as it is shown in the previous Figure 12. The value from the k-rad superblock is multiplied by the Astronomical Unit to the power of -2. The radiation acceleration is calculated by this multiplication.

Astronomical Unit of Mars calculation;

$$1AstronomicalUnit = 149597871km$$

$$MarsAstronomicalUnit = 1.52 \times AstronomicalUnit$$

$$1.52 \times 149597871 = 227388763.92km$$

Figure 15: *Sail-Logic Diagram*

This block diagram part is about sail-logic. This diagram decides when the solar-sail will be on and off position. When it is on position solar-sail faces to the Sun and collects the sunlight. When it is off position solar-sail turns back to the Sun and gets zero sunlight.

Figure 16: (*Sail-Logic*).

Figure 15 shows when the solar-sail is in on and off positions. When it is equals to 0 it is off position, when it is equals to 1 it is on position. To approach to Mars atmosphere solar-sail starts with off position and after that it goes to on position. Thus, while the periapsis value decreases rapidly, the apoapsis value increases slowly, which allows getting closer to Martian atmosphere. When it is equal to zero θ equals to 0 degrees, when it is equals to 1 θ equals to 90 degrees.

Figure 17: *Oribt Of Solar-Sail around Mars*

As it is explained in the Figure 15, in this figure while the periapsis value decreases rapidly, the apoapsis value increases slowly, which allows getting closer to Martian atmosphere.

3.3.6 Illustration of realistic light sail thrust [11]

[32]The primary source to take into account is McInnes (1999, Sec. 2.6.1) [6]. Two components make up the total force caused by radiation pressure, and they are separated along the normal and tangential directions to a completely flat sail:

$$\mathbf{f} = f_n \hat{\mathbf{n}} + f_t \hat{\mathbf{t}} \quad (1)$$

Notice that this notation is slightly different as $f_{n,t}$ is written as scalars multiplied by the versors $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}$.

The components f_n and f_t of the total force acting in the directions normal and tangential to the sail are provided therein as:

$$f_n = PA \left[(1 + \tilde{r}s) \cos^2 \alpha + B_f(1 - s)\tilde{r} \cos \alpha + (1 - \tilde{r}) \frac{\epsilon_f B_f - \epsilon_b B_b}{\epsilon_f + \epsilon_b} \cos \alpha \right], \quad (2)$$

$$f_t = PA(1 - \tilde{r}s) \cos \alpha \sin \alpha \quad (3)$$

where it is assumed for $P(r)$ the asymptotic expression (McInnes (1999), Eq. (2.41)) [6] :

$$P(r) \simeq \frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{L_S}{4\pi R_S^2} \right) \left(\frac{R_S}{r} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

and L_s , R_S , and $r = |\mathbf{r}|$ are the luminosity and radius of the Sun and the magnitude of the radius vector, respectively. Also, following parameters are defined:

A : area of the sail

α : angle from the normal

$\tilde{r} \in (0, 1)$: reflection coefficient

s : fraction of initially absorbed photons that are reflected specularly

$B_{f,b}$: front and back non-Lambertian coefficients

$\epsilon_{f,b}$: front and back emissivities. In what follows, as a first step, it should

be considered sails that are non-ideal because their reflection coefficient is less than unity. However, the assumption must be retained that the sail be Lambertian, so that $B_{f,b} = 0$ so that the second and third term in Eq. (2) vanish. Also, all photons are assumed to be initially absorbed are reflected specularly, so that $s = 1$. Therefore Eqs. (2-3) become:

$$f_n = PA(1 + \tilde{r}) \cos^2 \alpha \quad (2b)$$

$$f_t = PA(1 - \tilde{r}) \cos \alpha \sin \alpha \quad (3b)$$

This also corresponds to neglecting the radiation pressure due to thermal re-emission of absorbed radiation.

Figure 18: *Tangential and normal components of the solar radiation pressure*

In Figure 18, it is shown that the effect of the reflection, when reflection coefficient get closer to 1, the effect becomes much smaller.

3.4 Attitude Dynamics

The workflow of attitude dynamics of this project is shown in the Figure 19. The sensors and navigation together determine the attitude. Then, to reach the desired attitude, “control” is applied and the actuators start rotation. At the end, sensors measure the new attitude and the loop starts again.

Figure 19: *Spacecraft Control System redesigned from Karaaliler et. al. [33]*

3.4.1 Actuator [8]

Actuators are mechanisms that can send a torque to the spacecraft. In this project, momentum wheels are used as actuators. Momentum wheels can provide attitude control in the wheel spin axis beside the bias momentum. The actuator needs to apply enough torque for the attitude control. The actuator’s energy is generated by solar panels and the battery.

Based on the Lightsail 2, some researches for the actuator are done. According to Sinclair Interplanetary [34], a reaction wheel that can generate a momentum of 0.4 Nms with a heavy rotor has the dimensions 46mm high \times radius of 103 mm (mounting feet are not included) and weighs 770 g. This wheel is supposed to have a supply voltage between 24 V and 34 V.

3.5 Attitude Control with Feedback Mechanism [8]

The main control strategy of the spacecraft is On-Off control. To pass from the “On” position to the “Off” position, so that the solar sail minimizes the thrust, an attitude control mechanism is applied to the system. Since it is a rotational system, it works with the following relation:

$$\tau = I \times \theta'' \tag{1}$$

I, the total moment of inertia was computed in Section 3.2.1, so torque can be found with basic integral calculation.

$$\tau \div I = \theta'' \quad (2)$$

$$\int_{t=0}^t \frac{\tau}{I} dt = \theta' \quad (3)$$

$$\int_{t=0}^t \int_{t=0}^t \frac{\tau}{I} dt dt = \theta \quad (4)$$

$$\tau = \frac{2 \times I \times \frac{\pi}{2}}{t^2} \Big|_{t=0}^t \Big|_{t=0}^t \quad (5)$$

The torque applied for 1800 s is calculated as

$$\tau = 0.0200524 Nm \quad (6)$$

This relation can be simulated as an open-loop as shown below.

Figure 20: *Xcos diagram without feedback mechanism*

This simulation gives the following output.

Figure 21: *Xcos output without feedback control*

As it is seen from the plot, rotation does not stop at $\pi/2$. In order to stop the rotation when theta is $\pi/2$ a feedback control is applied in Section 3.5.1.

3.5.1 Attitude Control without Torque Disturbances

If the disturbance torque and sensor errors are neglected, the only effect on the spacecraft is reference input that is applied via the momentum wheel. The relation between the torque, the moment of inertia, and the angle is explained above. In this section, a feedback mechanism is going to be designed based on these three parameters. To design a feedback mechanism, the transfer function of the system must be written. The transfer function of the system is the ratio of the Laplace transformation of the response function to the Laplace transformation of the driving function. The driving function of the system in this section is the torque applied and the response is the theta angle. Another name for the torque applied is control torque. The transfer function of the system is shown below.

$$I\theta'' = T_c + T_d \quad (7)$$

where T_c is control torque and T_d is torque disturbance. Laplace transform of the equation is

$$Is^2\Theta(s) = T_c(s) + T_d(s) \quad (8)$$

Where $Y(s)=\Theta(s)$ and $U(s) = T_c(s)$

$$Y(s) = \frac{1}{I s^2}(U(s) + T_d(s)) \quad (9)$$

When torque disturbance T_d is zero,

$$Y(s) = \frac{1}{I s^2}U(s) \quad (10)$$

The transfer function is

$$G(s) = \frac{Y(s)}{U(s)} \quad (11)$$

So,

$$G_p(s) = \frac{1}{I s^2} \quad (12)$$

Here, G_p represents the plant transfer function. When the control blocks are added, the control transfer function of G_c is written. The attitude of the spacecraft without torque disturbances is controlled with proportional-derivative “PD” control. Proportional-derivative “PD” controller is formulated as

$$G_c(s) = K_p + sK_d \quad (13)$$

This formula is a different expression of spring and damper where the proportional represents the spring and the derivative represents the damper. A block diagram of the “PD” control mechanism is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: *Block diagram of PD feedback control [35]*

In the block diagram, $R(s)$ represents the reference input and $Y(s)$ is the output. Same diagram also can be represented as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: *Alternative block diagram of PD feedback control*

G_c and G_p can be rearranged with respect to the block diagram as following.

$$G_c(s) = K_p \quad (14)$$

$$G_p(s) = \frac{1}{I s^2 + K_d s} \quad (15)$$

The feedback mechanism based on the block diagram is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: *Feedback mechanism*

In order to see the process better, same simulation can be built as follows.

Figure 25: *Feedback mechanism where the velocity and angular acceleration can be measured.*

The clock block arranges the period and initialization time, scopes display the plots, and “To Workspace” blocks export the data to a .txt file. These data files are later used to calculate errors.

First, the reference input which is the desired attitude is applied. The desired attitude here is $\pi/2$.

So, $\pi/2$ Nm torque is applied.

Figure 26: *Torque applied/Reference Input*

Then, K_p and K_d values are applied. K_p is 6 and K_d is 220. The values for the PD are found by try and error method. In PD Control, K_p controls the oscillations and K_d controls the settling time. By increasing the K_p , the system can have more oscillations and by manipulating the K_d value, settling time can change. Higher K_d values decrease the settling time.

Figure 27: *Proportional and derivative*

These are summed and divided by the inertia. So far, the output is angular acceleration.

Figure 28: *Inertia*

After the first integration, it is angular velocity. The second integration gives the output, theta angle.

Figure 29: *Integration*

The feedback control gives the following results.
The angular acceleration:

Figure 30: *Angular acceleration vs time*

The angular velocity:

Figure 31: *Angular velocity vs time*

The theta angle:

Figure 32: *Theta vs time*

Output data can be written to .txt files via “To Workspace” blocks. From the output data file, theta angle at $t = 1800$ s which is the settling time is determined and the error is calculated. The error of this feedback mechanism is

$$e(t) = \theta_d(t) - \theta(t) = r(t) - y(t) \quad (16)$$

With Laplace transform

$$E(s) = R(s) - Y_r(s) \quad (17)$$

The desired θ angle here was $\pi/2$ which is approximately 1.57079632679489 meanwhile measured output at $t=1800$ s is 1.57100139073581. So, the error is:

$$e = 1.57079632679489 - 1.57100139073581 = -0.00020506394$$

In terms of percentage: 0.0130548%.

This error is negligible because the sensors do not measure this accurately as shown later. The other terms of this feedback that can be defined are “undamped natural frequency” and “damping ratio”. Undamped natural frequency ω_n and damping ratio ξ are defined as follows.

$$\omega_n^2 = \frac{K_p}{I} \quad (18)$$

$$2\xi\omega_n = \frac{K_d}{I} \quad (19)$$

When K_p , K_d and I values are substituted, ω_n and ξ are found as:
 $\omega_n = 0.017$ and $\xi = 0.31228$

If the damping ratio is between 0 and 1, the system is called underdamped. Transfer function in terms of ω_n and ξ can be written as:

$$T(s) = \frac{\omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2\xi\omega_n s + \omega_n^2} \quad (20)$$

or

$$T(s) = \frac{2.9 \times 10^{-4}}{s^2 + 0.0106s + 2.9 \times 10^{-4}} \quad (21)$$

Underdamped systems have two complex conjugate roots which means the system is stable. As the results above show, theta angle stabilized before 1800 s.

Now, the attitude control without the torque disturbances and measurement errors is completed. In Section 3.5.2 these effects are going to be added to the system to have a realistic output.

3.5.2 Attitude Control with Torque Disturbances and Measurement Errors

In this section, measurement errors caused by sensors such as sun sensors and torque disturbances such as perturbations are included to the control mechanism. Torque disturbances create a steady-state error so integral control is applied. That makes the control mechanism “PID”.

Following diagram shows the feedback mechanism with torque disturbances and measurement errors.

Figure 33: *PID Feedback control with torque disturbances and noise*

Figure 35: *Desired output and realistic output*

Red lines represent the pulse commands. Here, 3600 s is one period and each period has 1 pulse for 1800 s. On the other hand, black lines represent the realistic sailing performance. When the figure is compared to the solar sailing performance of the LightSail 2 in Reference [1] it can be seen that the black lines approach the real outputs. In each period, black lines draw a different plot since the noise and the torque disturbances are generated with random generators. Because of the realistic effects, solar sailing does not operate ideally. In reality, even in the “Off” position, the sail never reaches 0 because of the vibrations. As a result, the simulation gives a realistic sailing performance as it was aimed at the beginning of the project.

3.6 Visualization via Blender

In this project, Blender has been used as an animation program for video that introduces the operation. Blender is a helpful program for open-source works. An animation video was created for the operation. Firstly the Sun, the Earth, and Mars have been created and the layout has been adjusted. Solar Sail stl file has been imported and created for the movement. After these steps, for animation keyframes for movements have been added and rendered. Animations have been exported and assembled. Next sections explain processes one by one.

3.6.1 Creating the Sun

The solar system animation starts with a sphere adjusted and smoothed for a polished appearance. Default lighting is removed, and a 'sun' material is assigned to the sphere. In the modifier part select smooth for UV sphere. A force field was added to create a fire effect. Flow settings were arranged.

Figure 36: *Force Field of the Sun*

In the shader part, nodes were arranged to create the material of the Sun. HD image was used and colors were selected for the atmospheric scene.

Figure 37: *Material of the Sun*

The Sun was rendered and sharpened for a 3D effect. In the composite part glare and sharpen nodes were used.

Figure 38: *Compositing the Sun*

3.6.2 Creating the Earth and Mars

In this part, inner planets were created, and the Earth was rendered using an image texture. First, two suns were created, one on the Earth and one on Mars. For the Earth, an image texture from Nasa 3D assets was used and attached to the Earth. The viewport shading was changed back to the

rendered view to focus on the Earth. The node editor in Blender allows users to create various tools and objects using the material output node and the principled BSDF shader.

Figure 39: *The Earth Material*

Figure 40: *Atmosphere of the Earth*

Figure 41: *Mars Material*

3.6.3 The Layout

Figure 42: *Layout View*

3.6.4 Solar Sail Adjusting

Solar Sail Concept file imported as an .stl file to Blender [36]. Firstly, the Sail was resized and located near the Sun object. To give Solar Sail circular movement respect to the Sun, a bezier circle was added on the board and enlarged. Solar Sail should have its center at the world origin, with no transformation in any direction for following this circle. Secondly, in Solar Sail object constrain was added and selected 'follow path'. As a target object, a bezier circle is chosen. Thirdly, in the curve option place, click the animate path button. Finally, the Solar Sail was moving around on the circular path exactly as wanted.

Figure 43: *Solar Sail and the Earth*

3.6.5 Solar Sail Movement

Two bezier circles were added for visualizing the two-stage orbit movement. The first orbit is named 'Bezier Circle' and the second orbit has been named 'Bezier Circle 2'. The second orbit has a bigger apoapsis length but their periapsis lengths are equal. The figure below shows their specifications and arrangement by the Sun. Sail has begun its journey with the first rotation. In the beginning, the sail is at 0 degrees and turns its face to the Sun at 45 degrees. In the second rotation part, the sail turns 90 degrees to turn its backside. By these rotations, the sail pumps energy, and the orbit is enlarged. This means operational energy for a sail can be ready to take the journey to Mars. (Operational simulation has been performed on Xcos)

Figure 44: *Solar Sail Rotations*

3.6.6 Star Texture

Creating stars is a significant step to visualize for the space environment background. The texture nodes are given in the image below.

Figure 45: *Background Stars*

3.6.7 Rendering

The process of converting a 3D scene into a 2D picture is called rendering. Three distinct render engines, each with varying strengths, are included in Blender. A real-time renderer with a physical basis is called EEVEE. Cycles is a path tracer with a physical foundation. Workbench is intended for modeling, layout, and previewing.

Additional renderers from outside developers can be acquired as add-ons. To regulate render performance and quality, each renderer has its render parameters. The cameras, lights, and materials in a render determine its appearance. While EEVEE and Cycles share these, other features are exclusive to one or the other.

Renders can be divided into passes and layers, which can then be combined with actual video or composited together for artistic control. You can add non-photorealistic line rendering using Freestyle.

All render engines that Blender supports may use interactive 3D viewport rendering to quickly iterate on lighting and shading. After that, rendering and production of the final, high-quality image or animation are possible.

When a computer renders a scene, it determines how much light is there in order to produce the final image or animation. The render engine needs information from the scene in order to calculate the lighting. This covers items such as:

1. Geometry
2. Materials
3. Light setup
4. Textures
5. World background

In this project, planets and the Sun were rendered by using these techniques. First, a geometrical shape was adjusted, and inserted proper material for the object. The light setup was used for visualization properly. By texturing part object gained a more realistic scene.

3.6.8 Animation

One of the Two bezier circles was added to visualize the two-stage orbit movement. The first orbit is named 'Bezier Circle' and the second orbit is named 'Bezier Circle 2'. The second orbit has a bigger apoapsis length but

their periapsis lengths are equal. The figure below shows their specifications and arrangement by the Sun.

Sail has begun its journey with the first rotation. In the beginning, the sail is at 0 degrees and turns its face to the Sun at 45 degrees. In the second rotation part, the sail turns 90 degrees to turn its backside. By these rotations, the sail pumps energy, and the orbit is enlarged. This means operational energy for a sail can be ready to take the journey to Mars. (Operational simulation has been performed on Xcos)

In the animation part, the sail follows the bezier circle 1 path while finishing the first orbit. Then, the sail begins to follow the Bezier Circle 2 path. In the below picture, animation settings can be seen. Animation contains the whole process.

Figure 46: *Animation Settings*

3.6.9 Rendering the Animation

After the settling up the animation keyframes, the render engine works to create animated videos. Cycles rendering engine uses the CPU as a device. 128 samples have been taken for a frame. For the Sun scene, 200 frames have been rendered. For 8-second animation video, render time took about 5 hours.

Figure 47: *Renderig Process*

3.6.10 VR Process in Blender [12] [13] [14]

Blender can provide a God-like perspective thanks to VR Goggles in order to understand the logic of the CubeSat. To pass from real world to Blender universe, first VR Goggle Equipments are plugged to the computer.

In this project, Oculus Rift S model goggle is used. This goggle set has 1 VR Google, 2 sensors, and 2 Oculus touch controllers. Sensors are connected to the computer from a USB port. Also, the google is connected to the computer via 1 USB and 1 HDMI ports.

Oculus Rift S is activated with the applications “Oculus” and “SteamVR”. OpenXR is also an equivalent of SteamVR but in this project, SteamVR is preferred.

After connecting the goggles equipment to the computer, Oculus and SteamVR applications are run. Now, the computer is ready to connect the Blender universe to the VR Goggles.

To create a VR scene in Blender, the following steps are applied.

1. Open Blender 4.0
2. Go to Edit > Preferences > Add Ons

 * (Unsaved) - Blender 4.0

Figure 48: *Edit*

3. Select 3D View: VR Scene Inspection

Figure 49: *Preferences*

Then, VR tab should be seen in right bar.

4. Click VR Tab

Figure 50: *VR TAB*

5. Start VR Session Here you are in the Blender world. If Blender does not start the VR Session and says “Failed to connect to an...” this means there is something wrong with the connection cables or SteamVR connection.

Oculus Touch controllers do not have the function of Blender properties. So, with the controllers, you can wander around but you cannot change any feature of the visual universe.

4 Results and Discussion

The Xcos simulation provides a detailed understanding of the solar-sail maneuvers using two-body dynamics. By adjusting the Sun's and Mars' parameters, the simulation gave outputs of solar-sail's orbits and sail logics. With the application of sail logic, the sail orients its body to maximize and minimize the sunlight from time to time.

In this project, orbiting around the Sun and Mars has been done. For furthermore improvements, aerobraking can be done with an Xcos block diagram. Also, Attitude Control with Feedback Mechanism Xcos diagram can be merged with Solar-sail Orbiting the Sun Xcos Diagram and Xcos Diagram of Approach to Mars Atmosphere to get more realistic outputs. Coupling the translational and rotational motions can help to analyze the realistic behavior of the solar sail during the mission. When the reflection coefficient is changed to less than 1, the simulation approaches to the real application.

Overall, incorporating solar sails into space missions is a promising route for long-term and cost-effective exploration. Successful demonstrations and extensive simulations highlight this technology's potential to revolutionize space travel and satellite operations.

4.1 Blender for Engineering Purposes

To help people make better decisions regarding complicated systems, engineers can concentrate on elucidating the systems' real operation. Blender advocates for the open-source community.

Blender software is a useful tool for engineers since it allows them to model and visualize mechanical assemblies and components in three dimensions. Blender may be used to produce realistic and detailed depictions of prototypes, machinery, and product ideas. For instance, several software programs are needed by mechanical engineers when they are designing.

A 3D model of an engine can be made by an engineer, and it can be animated to reflect the crankshaft, piston, and other internal combustion engine characteristics. Certain businesses employ certain kinds of software for particular tasks. An engineer would benefit from learning Blender if they wanted to work in that industry.

Blender's simulation and animation features can also be used for producing educational materials, demonstrating functionality, and testing mechanical systems. In general, engineers may find Blender to be a useful tool for designing, analyzing, and presenting their work.

4.2 Animation via Scripting Between SCILAB and BLENDER

In the publication [37] “Software Set Up” explains how a realistic simulation environment was developed for the validation of the navigation algorithms in the mission. Sabatini has used MATLAB. The software logic can be modified to work with Scilab and Blender. Scilab is an open-source alternative to MATLAB and can be used for numerical computations including orbital dynamics simulation. Blender has been already mentioned as a 3D graphics software. A generic way to combine Scilab for trajectory calculations and Blender as an animation tool is as follows:

Figure 51: *Software Logic*

To implement this writing the custom scripts in Scilab and Blender is needed to exchange data and automate the animation process. Blender provides a Python scripting interface that can be used to write custom scripts and Scilab uses its scripting language. The details of implementation would vary depending on the complexity of the mission scenario and the desired simulation realism level.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, a digital twin is built to prove the concept of the mission as it is explained in the paper. A digital twin is an advanced simulation that is anything that happens in real application is simulated in the digital universe. The digital twin is created based on three titles; orbital dynamics, attitude dynamics, and visualization. Orbital dynamics is the part where translational motion is explained and simulated. On the other hand, the rotational motion is realized in attitude dynamics. Scilab/Xcos and WFE which are FOSS are used in both parts.

After the introduction, literature related to solar sailing is reviewed. In “The Mission” part, the working principle and history of Solar-Sail is explained. Other subjects that are mentioned in this paper are “On-Off Control Strategy” and “Aerobraking”. The design of the satellite is improved and the moment of inertia is calculated. In Section 3.3, orbital maneuvers, coplanar maneuvers and elliptical to circular transfer are clarified. Since the spacecraft first orbits the Sun, this simulation is analyzed with its outputs. The next step after the Sun is Mars.

The success in the orbital dynamics is the simulation of orbiting around Mars where the semimajor axis decreases in every period. Then, realistic light sail thrust is illustrated in the Jupyter Notebook. This part points out the impact of the reflection coefficient on solar radiation pressure force.

Next, the attitude dynamics are demonstrated. The actuator of this sail is a reaction wheel developed by Sinclair Interplanetary [34]. Attitude control with a feedback mechanism is one of the main subjects that is studied in this paper to create the digital twin.

Besides that, the realistic attitude is simulated in the attitude dynamics part with the feedback mechanism by adding torque disturbances and measurement errors. Also, an infinite time interval is assigned for this rotation. The output of the realistic attitude control is compared with the measured data of the LightSail 2 in Section 3.5.2.

Finally, the orbital dynamics and the attitude dynamics are visualized in Blender. The steps of creating the space environment and solar sail movements are explained. Scenes are rendered and animated frame by frame.

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